

GLOBAL GAP INTERNATIONAL STANDARD PLACE IN AGRICULTURE.

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Annotation: Ensuring quality in the production of products in the economy, improving the quality of products, GLOBAL GAP, based on the requirements of international standards, has introduced a quality management system in farms producing agricultural products and its certification has an important place in the development of production technologies, increasing the export potential of manufactured products and ensuring their competitiveness.

Key words: quality, product, planning, mechanism, conformity, certificate, resource, standard, international standard, normative document, technical documents, object, system.

The GLOBAL GAP international standard is a recognized international standard to ensure the safety of cultivated agricultural products and their compliance with existing quality and technical requirements. The GLOBAL GAP standard was created based on the requirements of international standards. Certification according to standards is voluntary, the difference from national standards is that certification not only evaluates the quality of final products, but also covers the entire period of production, which is considered important. GLOBAL GAP consists of standards adopted in the European Union for the cultivation of agricultural products that guarantee minimal damage to the environment [1]. The first certified farms in Europe appeared in 2003 and reached the international level in 2006. The European standard began to spread around the world, and in 2007 it was decided to change its name to GLOBAL GAP. Currently, producers in many countries of the world are certified by the GLOBAL GAP

system, the total number of certified farms exceeds 170,000. According to the available data, the share of plant products (including fruits and vegetables) of the total number of certified farms was about 75 percent, the share of livestock products was 15 percent, and the share of aquatic crops was 10 percent. The main elements of the standards include the analysis of risks in production, labor protection and production sanitation, environmental protection, product tracking and return procedures, the origin and quality of crop material, the suitability of the soil for the production of agricultural products, including the availability of a developed system for soil analysis and soil fertilization, water, pesticide and solid material residue, microflora analysis, implementation and application of an integrated system of plant protection, collection, processing and storage of products [2]. The GLOBAL GAP certification system is a means of confirming or denying a conclusion about product safety based on the monitoring of production technology, thereby demonstrating that the producer is a supporter of acceptable agricultural practices. At the same time, the main driving factor of the GLOBAL GAP standard is trade networks, processing enterprises and catering enterprises. Ensuring the safety of products on the shelves is one of the main requirements of most leading companies and retail chains. Implementation of the GLOBAL GAP international standard consists of preparation, pre-certification work, and certification stages. The preparatory stage consists of diagnostic audit, training of employees, development of documents and introduction of standard requirements. During the diagnostic audit, an initial acquaintance with the farm takes place [3]. Acquaintance with the specialty, certified crops, state of machine-tractor park and existing equipment, state of the labor protection system, organization of the entire work chain in the field takes place. Preparation of the farm, training of employees and introduction of compliance criteria are the main stages of building the GLOBAL GAP system. In this case, the farm is analyzed in detail according to all control points, including the understanding methodology that provides systematic identification, assessment and management of risks that have a significant impact

on product safety, and is aligned with standard requirements. Also, production risks are analyzed, appropriate rules for monitoring and returning products, document circulation and registration systems of technological events are introduced, necessary elements are introduced to determine the level of residues in products. After the farm's compliance with the control clauses of the standard, a special inspection form is filled out and an order is sent to the organization conducting the inspection for certification. GLOBAL GAP Certificate Key Benefits and Limitations GLOBAL GAP is the owner of the standard and does not issue certificates itself, but it has delegated the authority to issue certificates to registered certification bodies and companies. Before contacting a certification company that conducts audit and certification processes, it is recommended to first read and familiarize yourself with the general requirements and control points of GLOBAL GAP. Farmers who want to meet the requirements of the GLOBAL GAP standard and receive certification must be prepared for certain financial costs. In particular, farmers must pay for the costs of preparation of cultivated areas and production infrastructure, training of employees, development of a documentation system in accordance with standard requirements, and then registration, inspection and certification [4]. In this case, it should be noted that an application for certification can be submitted as an individual producer or a group of producers, the cost of certification depends on the chosen body and company, the time spent on inspection, and the size of cultivated areas to be certified. In addition to the certification fee charged by the certification body and the company, farmers must also pay an annual registration fee to extend the validity of the certificate. GLOBALG.A.P. guidelines, standards and regulations have great benefits. Among them, there are opportunities to increase the quality of products and ensure food safety, facilitate access to markets, reduce the risks of using prohibited pesticides, and control the maximum amount of chemical and toxic substances in the composition. The certified manufacturer is now GLOBALG.A.P. has priority in selling its products to international retail chains that require certification.

GLOBALG.A.P. For the purposes of certification, a producer or group of producers is required to establish an effective administrative system to monitor and record all agricultural activities [5]. As a result, certification requires a significant amount of effort, administrative and financial resources from the point of view of a single enterprise, so certification is much easier for large producers or groups of producers [6].

It should be noted that GLOBALG.A.P. certification does not guarantee a higher profit than the market price for the manufactured product, because the standard represents a minimum set of requirements for sustainable production and development of business relations in business. Key terms in the field of quality and consumer interest in quality. Based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a wide path has been opened to expand the implementation of quality management systems in accordance with international standards in the enterprises of the Republic. To increase the competitiveness of the products and services provided by the enterprises of our country, to increase their export potential and to introduce quality management systems in accordance with international standards in the enterprises of the Republic [7].

The updated composition of the special working group on the coordination of the implementation of quality management systems was announced, and the following were defined as the main tasks of the special working group. Coordination of the implementation of quality management systems in accordance with international standards in republican enterprises and their timely certification. Systematic monitoring of processes related to timely development, implementation and certification of quality management systems in accordance with international standards in manufacturing enterprises [8].

Develop proposals to encourage manufacturing enterprises that have implemented quality management systems in accordance with international standards. Engagement of a consultant with appropriate qualifications for the development and implementation of quality management systems in accordance

with international standards in society was carried out on the basis of an open competition. Certification of quality management systems in accordance with international standards was carried out by accredited certification bodies in accordance with the procedure established by law. In conducting tenders for the purchase of products for state needs, under other equal conditions, it was assumed that the priority would be given to the product suppliers of our country with a certified quality management system. In accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to introduce quality management systems in accordance with international standards" in the calculation of profit tax, the taxable profit of legal entities is reduced to the amount of investments in the introduction and support of quality management systems in accordance with the procedure established by law. The list of technological equipment, components and spare parts that are exempted from customs duty and value added tax upon import into the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes equipment used in laboratory research and product testing, as well as components and spare parts for them. The National Information Agency of Uzbekistan decided to cover the experience of enterprises in the production of quality management systems in accordance with international standards every month in the mass media [9]. Today, in the world, including in our Republic, great importance is attached to the quality of the products and services provided. Because high-quality products not only expand the export opportunities of our independent country, bring them to the world market, increase competitiveness, but also attract foreign investments to our Republic, which increases our country's foreign exchange reserves, and determines our economic position. In order to demonstrate the quality of their products to the public, they always participate in exhibitions and the best product review contests, they talk a lot about the fact that their manufactured products have certificates of conformity, and the services they provide are licensed. However, with the increasing competition in the world market, consumer demands for products are also increasing [10]. In most cases, we display the best manufactured products

specially prepared for our exhibitions, which we prepare for the exhibition under strictly controlled conditions, according to the standard requirements of all indicators. This also occurs during the certification process. At other times, the production of such products is more likely to go out of control by itself. And the consumer is a supporter of consuming quality products not only at the time of certification or exhibition, but also of products or services. We must not forget that consumer demand changes day by day. Therefore, it is necessary to constantly study the consumer requirements of the products we produce or the services we provide. Today's consumer requires a guarantee from the manufacturer that he can consistently buy a high-quality product. This is one of the main requirements of the market [11]. Our Government has adopted a number of Decisions regarding the introduction of international standards for economic development and increasing the export potential of manufacturing enterprises. Regular consideration of issues related to the implementation of quality management systems in accordance with international standards and the analysis of certification implementation at the quarterly meetings of complexes and the introduction of quality management systems in issuing work results at all levels of management it is indicated that the indicators should be used as an evaluation of the leaders' work. In conducting tenders for the purchase of products for state needs, in other equal conditions, preference is given to our product suppliers who have certified quality management systems in accordance with international standards and have the system [12].

Must develop, document, implement and maintain a quality management system in working condition, constantly improving its effectiveness in accordance with the requirements of this standard. It is necessary to determine the processes necessary for the quality management system and to apply them throughout the organization, to determine the sequence and interconnection of these processes, to determine the criteria and methods necessary to ensure the effectiveness of both the implementation and management of the processes, to maintain the operation of

the processes and to monitor them. provide available resources and information, monitor, measure and analyze processes; and must implement actions necessary to achieve planned results and continuous improvement of processes. The organization implemented the management of these processes in accordance with the requirements of this standard. If the organization decides to outsource the implementation of any process that affects product compliance, the organization must ensure that such processes are managed by itself. The type and extent of control should be determined within the framework of the quality management system. Processes related to the consumer [13]. Determining the requirements for the product, the requirements specified by the consumers, including the requirements for delivery and post-delivery activities, not specified by the consumer, specific or shall specify the requirements necessary for the intended use, the regulatory and regulatory requirements applicable to the product, if known, and any additional requirements necessary for the organization. Analyzing the requirements for the product, the organization must analyze the requirements for the product. This analysis should ensure that obligations to deliver the product to the customer are accepted or managed by the organization [14]. A documented procedure for identifying controls and appropriate responsibilities and authorities for handling nonconforming product should be developed. When appropriate, the organization shall resolve the issue of nonconforming product by one or more of the following methods [15]: taking action to eliminate the identified nonconformity, using it, producing it, if authorized by the appropriate competent authority and, where possible, by the consumer for deviation or to permit acceptance, to take action to prevent the original intended use or application, to take appropriate action to address the existing consequences or possible consequences of the nonconformity if the nonconforming product is discovered after delivery or during use. After the nonconforming product is eliminated, the product must be reverified to confirm compliance [16]. A working record of the description of the non-conformities and any subsequent action taken, including

deviation approvals, shall be maintained [17]. This program includes the development of a quality management system in enterprises and organizations, conducting audits in the certification of introduced quality management systems, types of audits, analysis of the results of internal audits conducted and carried out, assessment of the conformity of the quality management system based on the results of the analysis and approval procedures, the trend, perspective of the history and development of science, and the results of socio-economic reforms in our republic, and the impact of international and regional problems in the field of certification on the perspective of certification [18]. The importance of this subject covers the tasks of training bachelors in metrology, standardization, certification and product quality management related to the integration of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the international trade system.

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